

Immunological correlates of the HIV-1 replication-competent reservoir size

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Abbreviations:

ART	Antiretroviral therapy
AUC VL	Area under the curve viral load
HIV-1	Human Immunodeficiency virus type 1
IUPM	Infectious units per million resting CD4 ⁺ T-cells
QVOA	Quantitative viral outgrowth assay
VL	Viral load

ABSTRACT

Understanding what shapes the latent HIV-1 reservoir is critical for developing strategies for cure. We measured the frequency of persistent HIV-1 infection after 5 years of suppressive antiretroviral therapy initiated during chronic infection. Pre-treatment CD8⁺ T-cell activation, nadir CD4 count, and CD4:CD8 ratio predicted reservoir size.

Text

The greatest challenge to eradicating HIV-1 is the long-lived latent viral reservoir that is seeded early in infection, decays slowly after treatment initiation [1–3] and results in viremia if antiretroviral therapy (ART) is interrupted. There is an urgent need to understand factors contributing to the seeding and maintenance of the reservoir to inform strategies for HIV-1 cure.

A range of assays have been developed to quantify the latent HIV-1 reservoir, the reference standard for measuring replication-competent HIV being the quantitative viral outgrowth assay (QVOA) [4]. HIV-1 DNA and cell-associated RNA measures are more easily quantifiable, requiring lower blood volumes, and are more feasible for population-based studies. However, DNA-based assays overestimate the frequency of infected cells with replication-competent HIV-1 since most infected cells harbour defective proviruses, while QVOA underestimates the true size of the reservoir. Some measures of HIV-1 DNA, such as intact proviral DNA [5], correlate with IUPM [6] and track with the decay of IUPM on long-term ART. Here, we quantified the latent reservoir using QVOA since it measures only replication-competent virus [7], proviruses that will contribute to viral recrudescence upon ART cessation. The size of the HIV-1 latent reservoir, measured by HIV-1 proviral DNA, correlates inversely with nadir CD4⁺ T-cell count [8] and CD4:CD8 ratio [9]. Furthermore,

pre-ART viral loads (VL) correlate positively with HIV-1 DNA levels in CD4⁺ T-cells on ART [9]. Early initiation of ART results in a smaller HIV-1 reservoir [2], reducing the cumulative viral burden, preserving CD4⁺ T-cells, and maintaining CD4:CD8 ratios, while reducing T-cell activation [10,11].

There is a paucity of HIV-1 reservoir studies in African cohorts, particularly in African women who bear the greatest burden of disease globally. We measured reservoir size as the frequency of resting CD4⁺ T-cells harbouring replication-competent HIV-1 by QVOA, and investigated the association between clinical and immunological factors and replication-competent HIV-1 reservoir size in South African women virally suppressed on long-term ART.

METHODS

Full details are available in the Supplementary Materials.

Participants

We enrolled 20 women from the Centre for the AIDS Programme of Research in South Africa (CAPRISA) 002 acute infection cohort [12]. Peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) were obtained at the following six timepoints/participant, where available: acute infection, 1-year post-infection, and late chronic infection, as well as 2-, 4- and 5 years post-ART initiation (**Supplementary Table 1**). CD4 and CD8 counts and VL were available for multiple timepoints from the time of seroconversion.

Measurement of T-cell activation

PBMCs were thawed, rested overnight and stained for viability (LIVE/DEAD Fixable Violet stain), CD3-PE-Cy7, CD4-PE-Cy5.5, CD8-Qdot705, HLA-DR-APC-Cy7, CD38-FITC, CCR7-PE-CF594, and CD45RA-BV650. Data were acquired on a BD Fortessa and analysed

using FlowJo software (TreeStar, v10.5.3). Since naïve T-cells constitutively express CD38, T-cell activation was assessed on memory cells (CCR7⁺ CD45RA⁺ cells excluded).

Quantitative viral outgrowth assays

QVOA was performed using resting CD4⁺ T cells isolated from cryopreserved PBMCs obtained ~5 years after ART initiation, as previously described [13]. Bias-corrected maximum likelihood estimates for infectious units per million resting CD4⁺ T-cells (IUPM) were calculated in R using the SLDAssay package [14] based on the frequency of HIV-1 p24 capsid-positive wells on day 15 of the assay.

Modelling the replication-competent reservoir size

We employed the model given by equation [3] in Archin *et al.* [2], where we assumed that the latent reservoir half-life is 25 months before ART and 44 months during ART, to predict reservoir size in our cohort.

Study approval

This study was approved by the University of Cape Town (719/2017), the University of KwaZulu Natal (BE178/150), the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill (IRB 15-2717), and the Los Alamos National Laboratory (IRB LANL 13-18 E). All participants provided written informed consent prior to inclusion in the study.

RESULTS

This study utilized samples from twenty women living with HIV-1 (median age: 33 years [IQR, 30-39] who had been infected for a median of 4.4 years (IQR, 3.3-5.2) prior to treatment initiation. The frequency of resting CD4⁺ T-cells harbouring replication-competent

HIV-1 was determined by QVOA after a median of 5.1 years (IQR, 4.7-5.5) of ART, and 4.7 years (IQR, 4.2-5.2) of viral suppression (**Supplementary Table 1**). The relationship between reservoir size and clinical markers of infection (CD4⁺ T-cell count and VL) was investigated (**Table 1**). Reservoir size, represented as IUPM, correlated positively with overall viral burden (AUC VL) from infection to ART initiation, and also viral burden within the 12 months prior to ART initiation ($r=.549$; $P=.012$, and $r=.498$; $P=.026$, respectively). Furthermore, reservoir size correlated inversely with nadir CD4⁺ T-cell count ($r=-.597$; $P=.005$), and with the CD4:CD8 ratio at the time of ART initiation ($r=-.610$; $P=.004$) and at the time post-ART when the blood sample was collected that was used in the QVOA ($r=-.643$; $P=.007$). The inverse relationship between nadir CD4⁺ T-cell count and IUPM remained significant in a multivariate linear regression model adjusting for AUC VL (**Supplementary Table S2**).

Using the model in Reference [2], and longitudinal VL and CD4⁺ T-cell counts from the estimated time of infection, we predicted the frequency of latent cell infection. We observed a correlation between predicted and measured IUPM (**Supplementary Figure S1**) for VL and CD4⁺ T-cell counts modelled from acute infection to ART initiation ($r=.555$; $P=.012$; **Supplementary Figure S1A**) and from the year before to ART initiation ($r=.552$; $P=.013$; **Supplementary Figure S1B**). These correlations do not differ when extending the analyses to include on-ART VL and CD4⁺ T-cell count (**Supplementary Figures S1C and D**).

Extensive longitudinal sampling enabled investigation into whether memory CD4⁺ or CD8⁺ T-cell activation at multiple timepoints before and after ART initiation correlated with reservoir size. We measured surface expression of CD38 and HLA-DR on memory T-cells during acute infection, 1-year post infection, 1-year pre-ART initiation, and at 2- and 4-years post-ART initiation. Reservoir size correlated positively with the frequency of CD8⁺ T-cells

co-expressing HLA-DR and CD38 as well as those expressing HLA-DR alone, in the year preceding treatment initiation ($r=.709$; $P=.018$ and $r=.636$; $P=.040$, respectively; **Table 1**), remaining significant after adjusting for multiple comparisons.

Given that nadir CD4⁺ T-cell count and CD8⁺ T-cell activation may be influenced by viral burden over the course of untreated infection, we performed multivariable linear regression analyses (Supplementary **Table S2**) and found that nadir CD4⁺ T-cell count and memory CD8⁺ T-cell activation within a year prior to treatment initiation were significantly associated with reservoir size, even after adjusting for AUC VL (Supplementary **Table S2**). These models predict that a 1% increase in the frequency of CD38⁺HLA-DR⁺ memory CD8⁺ T-cells would result in a 0.033 log₁₀ increase in IUPM ($P=.0422$) after adjusting for CD4:CD8 ratio at ART initiation and AUC VL, while a unit increase in nadir CD4⁺ T-cell count resulted in a 0.004 log₁₀ decrease in IUPM ($P=.0420$) after adjusting for the frequency of CD38⁺HLA-DR⁺CD8⁺ memory T-cells and AUC VL (Supplementary **Table S2**).

DISCUSSION

Factors influencing HIV-1 reservoir seeding are understudied, particularly in African populations. In this study, we provide insights into the immunological characteristics correlating with the size of the replication-competent reservoir in a cohort of South African women who initiated treatment in late chronic infection.

We show that the cumulative viral burden measured over the entire course of HIV-1 infection or in the year prior to treatment directly predicted reservoir size. In addition, nadir CD4⁺ T-cell count and CD4:CD8 ratio before treatment initiation correlated inversely with replication-competent HIV-1 after prolonged viral suppression. Our findings build on previous

work that modelled VL and pre-ART CD4⁺ T-cell dynamics as key predictors of replication-competent reservoir size in the context of early ART [2] and identified the extent of CD4 depletion as shaping the HIV-1 DNA proviral load [8,9].

We hypothesized that greater T-cell activation pre-ART may enhance seeding of the HIV-1 reservoir by providing a larger pool of target CD4⁺ T-cells for infection, but the frequency of activated CD4⁺ T-cells was not significantly associated with IUPM at any timepoint before or after treatment initiation (data not shown). A limitation of this analysis is that CD4⁺ T-cell activation is highly dynamic due to continual depletion and migration of these cells, possibly limiting our ability to detect a significant relationship between CD4⁺ T-cell activation and reservoir size.

T-cell activation was measured at too few timepoints to use in our model predicting IUPM. Nevertheless, our multivariate linear regression analysis found that the link between CD8⁺ T-cell activation and reservoir size remained significant after controlling for viral burden, providing additional support for a direct link between CD8⁺ T-cell activation within the year before ART and reservoir size. Of note, we showed in nine women in this cohort, that 71% of unique viral outgrowth variants were genetically similar to viruses in circulation the year before ART initiation [13]. Together, the results suggest that immunological events late in infection may disproportionately shape the size and composition of the HIV-1 reservoir. We observed that the frequency of activated memory CD8⁺ T-cells in late chronic infection was positively associated with reservoir size. Hyperactivation, a strong predictor of disease progression, drives CD8⁺ T-cell dysfunction, and may explain the relationship between CD8⁺ T-cell activation and reservoir size [15]. CD38 and HLA-DR co-expression on CD8⁺ T-cells has been linked to an exhausted cell state and reduced cytotoxic ability [14], resulting in diminished

clearance of infected CD4⁺ T-cells during the transition to latency upon ART initiation in chronic infection, and potentially a larger latent reservoir.

Despite slight differences in methodology, our measured IUPM falls within the range of those reported by other studies including both males and females [2,17,18]. While our study did not compare reservoir size differences between females and males, two such studies have been published with discordant findings [17,18]. However, similar to this study, neither found a correlation between CD4⁺ T-cell activation and IUPM.

In conclusion, we demonstrate that replication-competent HIV-1 reservoir size during long-term suppressive ART associates with multiple immunological measures prior to ART, underscoring the need for early diagnosis and treatment. This new knowledge may assist with the design of novel cure and/or therapeutic vaccine approaches.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

NJG, QAK, and SSAK contributed samples and designed the study. SDI, SBJ, MM, and ODC collected experimental data. SDI, CR, NMA, ASP, TC, and FO analysed data and performed statistical analysis. SDI drafted the manuscript and all authors contributed to the final manuscript. DMM, MRA, LRM, RDS, CW, NJG, and WAB conceived and designed the study. All authors discussed the results and approved the final manuscript.

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POTENTIAL CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

ASP has equity stakes in Pfizer and GSK. He also received consulting income from Amphylx Pharmaceuticals. The other authors have declared that no conflict of interest exists.

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TABLE

Table 1. Demographic, clinical and immunological factors associated with replication-competent HIV reservoir size [as Log₁₀(IUPM)] (n=20)

	Spearman correlation		Univariate linear regression	
	Spearman's r	P-value	Coefficient	P-value
Age at QVOA (years) ^a	-0.1916	0.4185	-	-
Duration (months) ^b				
• Infection to ART initiation	-0.0361	0.8799	-	-
• from ART initiation to QVOA	0.0286	0.9046	-	-
• virally suppressed on ART before QVOA	-0.1734	0.4647	-	-
Plasma VL (log ₁₀ copies/mL)				
• at ART initiation ^c	0.3098	0.1838	-	-
• Cumulative (AUC VL) ^d				
Infection to ART initiation	0.5489	0.0122	0.3931	0.0220
1 year pre-ART	0.4977	0.0255	0.3047	0.0528
CD4 ⁺ T-cell count (cells/μL) ^e				
• Nadir	-0.5972	0.0054	-0.0040	0.0037
• ART initiation	-0.4271	0.0604	-	-
• at time of QVOA	-0.2947	0.2071	-	-
CD4:CD8 ratio ^f				
• ART initiation	-0.6102	0.0043	-1.7576	0.0017
• at time of QVOA	-0.6426	0.0065	-0.7612	0.0142
CD38 ⁺ HLA-DR ⁺ CD8 ⁺ T-cells (%) ^g				
Acute infection	0.1622	0.7286	-	-
1 year post-infection	-0.0788	0.8382	-	-
1 year pre-ART	0.7091	0.0182	0.0319	0.0288

^aAge of cohort: median 33 years, interquartile range (IQR) 30.3-38.5.

^bDuration of HIV infection to ART initiation: median 52 months, IQR 38.8-61.3; from ART initiation to the time of sizing by QVOA: median 61 months, IQR 56.3-65.8; from viral suppression to QVOA: median 56, IQR 50.3-61.5.

^cMedian VL at ART initiation: 4.7 log₁₀ copies/ml, IQR 4.2-4.9.

^dArea under the curve VL expressed as log₁₀ time-copies/ml; from infection to ART initiation (excluding peak VL during acute infection): 6.2, IQR 5.8-6.6; over the year prior to ART initiation: median 5.5, IQR 5.0-6.0.

^eAbsolute CD4+ T-cell count at nadir: median 243 cells/ μ L, IQR 182-280; at ART initiation: median 306, IQR 235-396; at time of sizing by QVOA: median 655, IQR 545-881.

^fCD4:CD8 ratio at ART initiation: median 0.3, IQR 0.2-0.4; at QVOA: median 1.0, IQR 0.8-1.3

^gFrequency of CD38+HLA-DR+ CD8+ memory T-cells at acute infection (2 months post-infection): median 26.5%, IQR 17.3-35.0; at 1 year post-infection: median 21.6, IQR 15.9-24.2; at 1 year prior to ART initiation: median 24.0, IQR 17.1-31.4.